

ISic3205

I.Sicily inscription 3205

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble (Luna?)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,system

Autopsy

2014.09.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 53270

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175822

EDR 073930

EDCS 13900107

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3205>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4357228](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357228)

Bibliography

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relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 1953.0159
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 297 fig.30

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